

Universität Potsdam

**PROTEST-AIRT
PROTESTING THE GLOBAL AIR TRANSPORT INDUSTRY:
SOCIAL MOVEMENTS FIGHTING FOR THE PRESERVATION OF
LOCAL COMMUNITIES AND THE PLANET**

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ABSTRACT

PROTEST-AIRT is a research project that explores the social movements campaigning against the global air transport industry in Europe. Before the pandemic, air transport was expected to grow globally, mostly because of more frequent flyers in existing markets and because of new markets in several regions of countries of the world. This future demand requires new infrastructural projects, consisting of new airports and airport expansions. Recently, several social movements have been campaigning all over the world to create awareness about the many 'side effects' associated to aviation, from the noise produced by airplanes to greenhouse gas emissions that contribute to global warming. Airports have become both the spaces and the recipients of diverse forms of dissent. As spaces of dissent, airports have been the place where activists congregate and practice their democratic rights, oftentimes engaging in 'radical' protest acts or civil disobedience. As recipients of dissent, the discourse about airports and airlines as key infrastructure for interconnection and development has been questioned by these political activists, who propose alternative readings of airports and airlines as spaces of environmental destruction and excessive consumption. The PROTEST-AIRT project investigates this European activism that targets the global air transport industry, including collectives such as SchipholWatch in the Netherlands, Am Boden Bleiben in Germany, Extinction Rebellion in United Kingdom, Zeroport in Spain and the organization Stay Grounded, which connects action groups from all over the world. PROTEST-AIRT includes an analysis of media texts, interviews, photographs of acts of dissent, social media accounts (in specific, Twitter) and other reports produced by airports, airlines, and social movements alike. The project will track the ongoing public debate about the potential solutions for the aviation industry and their limits.

IMPACT – SOCIETAL LEVEL

This research project aims at describing the state of global dissent against air transport and to compare this activism across countries. PROTEST-AIRT is interested in creating a detailed explanation or theory about these social movements, in relation to both the ‘post-pandemic’ recovery and the climate crisis. Because activism has gone global, the project also explores how these movements engage in networks of dissent and how they contribute to share a global public sphere, both by capturing international attention and fostering solidarity networks abroad.

PROTEST-AIRT is in synchrony with Europe 2030 targets, considering that these social movements are campaigning for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (net zero) and increasing the share of renewable energy and energy efficiency, including expanding rail transport. In terms of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals defined by United Nations, PROTEST-AIRT links to goals **11 Sustainable Cities and Communities**, **13 Climate Action** and **16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions**. PROTEST-AIRT encourages the development of a better, sustainable tourism, a key industry for Europe, setting parameters that could be adopted by other nations/regions while impacting Europe’s competitiveness and growth. PROTEST-AIRT gives voice to European social movements and empowers citizens in their bottom-up governance efforts (impacting Europe’s democratic institutions and political participation). It creates awareness about the important role played by media in their representation of political conflicts, mainly in their reporting of ‘radical’ acts of dissent and civil/democratic disobedience. The project will educate the citizenship apropos the relevance of the aviation industry and aims at making airports/airlines less contentious infrastructure/services. This project creates a bridge between the needs of European citizens and the tourism/aviation industry, therefore strengthening the collaboration between entrepreneurs and social scientists at local, European and global levels.

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- To understand the role that airports as **spaces of dissent and targets of dissent** (including airlines), while considering the economic and social relevance that global air transport has for the neighboring cities/Nation-states.
- To understand how the externalities/benefits of global air transport are discussed in the local, regional (European) and global public sphere, by following the **narratives/discourses related to the emergence of social movements** critical of the aviation industry.

RESULTS

All results from the PROTEST-AIRT project will be published in open access journals. The empirical data collected and a copy of any publication and results will be deposited online in a public repository. For more information about preliminary findings and results, check the website of the project: www.uni-potsdam.de/en/protest-airt

CONTACT INFORMATION

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